

DESCRIPTION OF MODERN MARKETING RESEARCH METHODS IN THE MARKET ECONOMY

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Abstract. This article examines the ability of these agencies to conduct marketing research with the help of specialized research agencies and to ensure the quality of such research, as well as their actions as executors.

Keywords: research, information, quality, agency, information, observation, resource, information.

ОПИСАНИЕ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ МЕТОДОВ МАРКЕТИНГОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ РЫНОЧНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается возможность этих агентств проводить маркетинговые исследования с помощью специализированных исследовательских агентств и обеспечивать качество таких исследований, а также их действия в качестве исполнителей.

Ключевые слова: исследование, информация, качество, агентство, информация, наблюдение, ресурс, информация.

INTRODUCTION

When conducting any scientific research, two sources of information are used to obtain information - primary and secondary. Secondary sources are existing data that always need to be studied first. In most cases, these data are collected for purposes other than the intended research areas. Therefore, it is necessary to collect new data or fill them with primary data. The difference between the sources of information has led to the existence of two different concepts - desk research and field research outside the office. As mentioned above, the cabinet study is conducted before the out-of-cabinet research for the purpose of collecting secondary data. Because the necessary information will be available even if it is necessary to systematize and fill it. In addition, these studies will determine exactly what information should be obtained during the inspection or examination. Also, printed materials are relatively easy to obtain as a source of information and can save time and money if used correctly.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cabinet research begins with examining the firm's own report. Although the appropriate departments are responsible for running the report, the marketing research department must ensure a sufficient level of unification of the reports and thereby create an information base for the firm. Reporting documents from which such basic information can be obtained must cover the following areas of activity.

- Purchase (stock level, rate of use, etc.).
- Production (quantity of production, materials, labor, transportation and storage of goods, their processing, packaging and packaging, overhead costs, use of equipment, etc.).
- Personnel (cost of labor force, lack of personnel, level of labor productivity, absenteeism).
- Marketing (sales promotion costs, administrative costs, specific market and brand information, etc.).

- Sales (value by individual goods, share of profit, volume of orders, type of sales channels or buyers, sales territories or agents).
- Finance (balance sheet information).

RESULTS

Qualitative research can help identify the most important commercialization needs. A distinctive feature of qualitative research is that it uses an inductive rather than deductive research philosophy. In addition, qualitative research has a more creative potential and requires the researcher to have an inner sensitivity in addition to intelligence. Five main methods of qualitative research are popular in international practice:

- 1) a comprehensive interview that allows you to conduct in-depth research in reality, identify new aspects of the problem, and provide accurate and meaningful assessments;
- 2) focus group interviews - its growing popularity in qualitative commercial research is explained by direct conversations in real time with real customers who can be observed with the help of a hidden video camera;
- 3) embedded observation, in which the researcher openly or covertly participates in everyday life for a sufficiently long time, observes the events taking place, listens to what is said, and asks questions related to the research task. This method allows for a more effective assessment of the real quality of the innovative product and the range of provided innovative services;
- 4) based on the situational analysis, its methodological direction, it provides the relations typical for works in the field of psychology;
- 5) projection techniques. This method is used in cases where the members of the focus group are asked to express their feelings, opinions and wishes regarding the new product.

In addition to the above-mentioned internal materials of the firm, the researcher also uses a large number of additional sources of information. They can be grouped based on the following main categories:

- Official data sources (domestic and foreign).
- Publications of universities and non-profit research organizations.
- Trade and Industry Association Publications.
- Academic, professional and commercial windows.
- Internet materials, results of surveys on social networks;
- Reports from commercial research organizations.

When using printed materials as a source of information, it is important to determine what method was used to collect and organize them. If the methods are not compatible, they should not be directly compared. In addition, it should be used only if the researcher is fully convinced of the reliability of this information. If after reviewing all printed sources of information the main problem is still not resolved, then research conducted outside the office is a prerequisite. Such areas are:

- * advertising research (analysis of the effectiveness of advertising announcements, study of advertising distribution tools, analysis of the use of mass media channels, determination of the size of the consumer audience);
- * consumer research (research of factors determining consumer choice and preference);
- * analysis of the efficiency of the distribution type (set) (comparison of alternative contents of the distribution type, load handling methods, etc.);

- * research of consumer characteristics (analysis of the idea of a new product, testing the product with the involvement of the consumer, determining the possible consumption and the classification of consumers of this product, etc.).

Primary data can be collected using one of the following three methods: observation, experiment, and sample research, as well as a combination of them. Observation is the simplest method and gives satisfactory results in most cases. The essence of this method is to observe the processes related to the studied factors. An example of this is the measurement of the flow of customers coming to the store, which is the main method used in the planning of commercial premises.

The observation technique depends on the observer's level of knowledge of his work and how truthfully he approaches the processes. A limitation of this method is its hidden nature. Because the observation should not have any impact on the minds of the buyers. In addition, external appearance often does not reveal the inner motive of buyers.

Experiments can be controlled. Experimentation is cheaper than sampling method. The main disadvantage of the experimental method is that it is impossible to restore the normal behavior of buyers in laboratory conditions. In most cases, such difficulties are solved by conducting the experiment in natural conditions. For example, packaging can be used to place trial samples on store shelves. Studying only one variable is very expensive and labor intensive. The reason for this is to test a large number of variables. For example, in the study of packaging, it is possible to determine the name, color, size, shape, information value and general effect that affect it separately. Currently, there are methods such as Latin square method, factor analysis method, which allow to conduct multi-factor analysis.

The most common method of obtaining primary data is sampling. Study methods are determined by three factors, depending on time and financial constraints:

1. Contingent of requested persons.
2. A means of establishing contact with the requested persons.
3. The nature of the necessary information and methods of obtaining it.

In theory, the most ideal way to collect primary data is to conduct a census of all individuals who need to be studied. In practice, it is almost impossible to implement such an event.

After selecting the persons to be surveyed, the researcher communicates with them using the following methods: personal interview, mail questionnaire, and telephone interview. We will begin our review of these methods with a telephone interview. The main disadvantage of this method is that the owners of personal telephones constitute only a certain group of the population. True, earlier they paid more attention to this factor. Today, telephone interviews are becoming more and more important in conducting quick and active surveys. Telephone interviews are useful in researching non-alcoholic beverage product markets. A phone interview should be short and to the point to be effective. Otherwise, the interviewer may be distracted and the interview may end prematurely.

The advantage of conducting a survey by mail is that it is possible to establish communication with any family and entrepreneur with very little effort. It also prevents the interviewer from changing the results of the survey. However, the main disadvantage of this method is the low response rate to mailed requests. A 50% response rate is a very good result. Due to the disadvantages of telephone and mail surveys, personal interviews remain the most common and acceptable method. Using expert interviews increases the percentage of favorable responses for research. The fact that the interviewer can clarify all the difficult questions will

increase the accuracy of the study and he will also be able to gather additional information. The main disadvantage of in-person interviews is the high cost and lack of experienced interviewers. However, many problems can be minimized by properly drafting the questionnaire. Most standard questionnaires contain not only questions but also alternative answers. any questionnaire requires four main elements. First, not every questionnaire can be anonymous. Therefore, they will have a name and a serial number. In addition, when the survey is conducted by the interviewer, the time and place of the interview and the interviewer's number and his signature should be included. Second, each questionnaire should have registration information about the persons being asked. These data are collected partly by survey and partly by observation and include: age, sex, social status, occupation of the head of the household, marital status, composition of the family, level and nature of education. surname and address of the applicant, information about being a renter or owner of a house, availability of real estate, provision of durable goods, although not mandatory, is considered useful information. Information about the applicant's income, while important, is considered an invasion of privacy by many.

Thirdly, the questionnaire should have control questions. This is necessary to make sure that the respondent is being consistent in his answers and that the questionnaire is being filled out according to the instructions. Fourth, the questionnaire should allow obtaining the necessary information for the solution of the studied problem.

After the collected data is systematized, summarized and analyzed, the results and recommendations based on them are presented in the form of a report. Most of the results of studies are presented to two groups - company managers and research specialists. Because these groups have different information needs and goals, two separate reports are prepared. The first is a fully documented report of a technical nature, and the second is an abbreviated report covering the main findings, conclusions and recommendations from the first report.

DISCUSSION

It was mentioned above that most companies conduct marketing research with the help of specialized research agencies. In order to ensure the quality of such research, these agencies will have the ability to conduct all the types of research mentioned above and act as executors.

In addition to fulfilling one-time orders of client companies, large agencies collect continuous systematic data in a certain area of marketing. The results of such studies are always sent to subscribers in the form of a standard report. An example of this is the British publication Inventory Audit of Retail Sales, which publishes data on retail inventory. In most cases, this bulletin is also called the Nielsen Index after the name of its founder.

Based on the market situation, the nature of the objectives and the tasks to be performed, and the defined strategy, the management of any enterprise that produces goods decides which marketing research to conduct and in what sequence, what human and financial resources to use, what to do on its own, which research to outsource. forced to decide what is useful to do. In order to save human and financial resources and achieve a great result in conducting marketing research, it is necessary to conceptually see how this problem will be in the future.

The development of this concept allows you to see marketing research in all its complexities and define ways to solve it in more rational ways. This is even more important.

When conducting complex and large-scale marketing research, it is desirable to develop a research concept, in which to reveal the problem in detail, to show ways and means of solving it

in the most effective way. On the basis of such a concept, it is possible to develop a research project, a method of conducting it, express tasks, collect, process and analyze information, develop proposals and recommendations. Below are the different ways to conduct marketing research.

Development of marketing research:

- ◆ Defining goals;
- ◆ Defining the problem;
- ◆ idea generation;
- ◆ Defining the system of indicators

The marketing research process traditionally includes the following steps:

- Obtaining and analyzing empirical data
- Development of working tools;
- Data acquisition process;
- Data processing and analysis
- Formation of main conclusions and formalization of research results
- Development of conclusions and recommendations;
- Formalization of research results

CONCLUSIONS

Marketers, statisticians, managers, distributors and specialists are usually involved in the collection of information. Effective use of the collected information requires only the results of the enterprise's goal achievement.

The difference between sampling and tracking is that the lower the cost of research and advertising, the more profitable it is for the company. Therefore, because there is only one or a small object in the sample tracking method, the enterprise will gain from the amount of time and excess cost.

1. The observational method of market research is carried out from the point of view of the product, competitors, the market itself and consumers. The observation method is the most widely used method of information collection in statistics of economic and social spheres. Observation, in turn, is differentiated according to a number of classification markers. In this regard, sufficient information is given in textbooks and manuals on economic statistics.

2. On the basis of observation, the information specific to the studied object or process can be obtained in total or in a selective form. Comprehensive monitoring is carried out based on the examination of all units of a particular complex. Such monitoring usually requires a lot of time, money, and its results serve to meet cross-sectoral needs. For example, population census, industrial and trade enterprises in the relevant area, etc.

3. During the development of the monitoring plan, important descriptions of the situations and conditions in which the activities of the monitored persons occur, that is, the issue of when and where monitoring should be conducted, should be decided.

Qualitative research methods such as in-depth interview, transcript analysis, projection method, and physiological measurements are briefly described below. An in-depth interview is performed by a skilled interviewer asking a group of respondents probing questions to understand why they behave in a particular way or what they think about a particular issue. The respondent is asked questions about the topic being studied, and he answers these questions

freely. "Why did you answer this way?", "Can you justify your point of view?" asks questions like

The first task in choosing a marketing research method is to familiarize yourself with some of the methods that can be used to collect marketing information. Then, based on the availability of resources, the most suitable among these methods is selected.

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